

Review Article

Inflammatory bowel diseases in horses: What do we know?

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Summary

Chronic inflammatory bowel diseases (IBDs) are a group of gastrointestinal (GI) disorders described in both humans and animals, but unlike in other species, in horses they are poorly defined and there is a lack of standardisation of the method of diagnosis. Although there is an impellent need of consensus on the nomenclature, diagnostic work-up, diet, treatment and management of horses with a suspected IBD, the aim of this review is to give initial guidelines for practitioners dealing with suspected cases. It provides a summary of the most relevant literature on the topic and presents the current knowledge on the clinical signs, diagnostic work-up, treatment and prognosis of IBDs in horses.

Introduction

Chronic inflammatory bowel diseases (IBDs) are a group of gastrointestinal tract (GIT) disorders described in both humans and animals (Craven and Washabau, 2019) as debilitating conditions characterised by recurrent episodes of GIT inflammation (Shapiro et al., 2016). In horses, IBDs are recognised as an infiltration of the mucosa and submucosa with different types of inflammatory cells (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000) and, although the pathogenesis is still unclear, the resulting bowel inflammation seems to be due to an altered immune reaction to unidentified antigens (Lindberg et al., 1985; Sairenji et al., 2017).

In the literature, there have been sporadic case reports since 1974 (Cimprich, 1974; Hodgson and Allen, 1982; Lindberg et al., 1985; Trachsel et al., 2010; van der Kolk et al., 2012; Bosseler et al., 2013; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Valle et al., 2013; Boshuizen et al., 2018; Fintl et al., 2020) with the last exhaustive review date of 2009 (Kalck, 2009). There is lack of standardisation of the methods of diagnosis, as clinical signs are nonspecific and results of different diagnostic tests are highly variable (Boshuizen et al., 2018). Furthermore, in contrast to dogs (Day et al., 2008), there are no clear guidelines for the interpretation of histopathological results of GIT biopsies. Moreover, limited information is available regarding the prevalence and response to treatment (Kaikkonen et al., 2014); thus, many cases with compatible clinical signs and presentation remain poorly defined (Metcalfe et al., 2013).

The aim of this review is to provide a summary of the most relevant literature on the topic and to present current knowledge on the clinical signs, diagnostic work-up, treatment and prognosis of IBDs in horses. Initial guidelines for practitioners dealing with suspected cases are suggested in this article.

Classification of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) in horses

There has been some confusion with respect to the nomenclature of the different types of IBDs in horses. In man, the term IBD is used mainly for two clearly defined conditions: ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease (Sairenji et al., 2017). Primary eosinophilic GIT disorders in people, characterised by an intense eosinophilic infiltration of one or multiple segments of the intestine, are considered separately (Kinoshita et al., 2019). In small animals, these types of intestinal diseases are grouped under the term of 'chronic enteropathies' and subdivided into food-responsive, antimicrobial-responsive and immunosuppressive-responsive according to the response to the treatment (Jergens and Simpson, 2012; Makielski et al., 2019). In horses, IBDs were originally grouped under the generic term of 'equine wasting syndrome' (Lindberg et al., 1985) and, when histological changes of the intestinal mucosa became progressively defined, different categories were created. Nevertheless, even in the most recent researches (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Olofsson et al., 2015), there is no uniformity in the terms used. For the diseases with eosinophilic infiltrations, different names have been used, including eosinophilic gastroenteritis, eosinophilic enterocolitis, eosinophilic granulomatosis, hypereosinophilia syndrome and exfoliative dermatitis and stomatitis (Schumacher et al., 2000; Schumacher and Legere, 2017). Generalised or localised exfoliative dermatitis associated with granulomatous inflammation of multiple organs has been referred to as granulomatous enteritis and equine sarcoidosis (Sloet van Oldruitenborgh-Oosterbaan and Grinwis, 2013).

Thus, the author suggests the following classification, based on the most relevant and recent literature (Schumacher et al., 2000; Proudman and Kipar, 2006; Kalck, 2009; Trachsel et al., 2010; van der Kolk et al., 2012; Archer et al., 2014; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Olofsson et al., 2015; Boshuizen et al., 2018): granulomatous enteritis (GE); lymphocytic-plasmacytic enterocolitis (LPE); and eosinophilic enterocolitis (EE) that can be, in turn, divided into multisystemic eosinophilic epitheliotropic disease (MEED) if there is involvement of other organs outside the GIT; diffuse eosinophilic enterocolitis (DEE) if the intestinal inflammation is generalised but no other organs are involved; and idiopathic focal eosinophilic enteritis (IFEE) or colitis (IFEC) if the inflammatory infiltrates are localised in a specific segment of the small or large intestine.

Granulomatous enteritis (GE)

This was the first type of IBD described (Cimprich, 1974) and the most frequently reported in the past century (Lindberg

et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000), while this form appears to have almost disappeared in more recent years (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014). It is characterised by lymphoid and macrophage infiltration at the level of the mucosal lamina propria with variable numbers of plasma cells and giant cells (Kalck, 2009; Meuten et al., 1978). There is marked villous atrophy, and the portion most severely affected is usually the ileum (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1985). Similarities with Crohn's disease in humans and Johne's disease in cattle have been described (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). Although GE is similar to other forms of IBDs, the cause is unknown, and most researchers hypothesise that an abnormal host inflammatory reaction to intestinal bacteria is the likely basis for the development of this condition (Kalck, 2009). Involvement of other organs is less frequently reported when compared with MEED, but the presence of hepatic and pulmonary granulomas also has been reported (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1985). Affected horses can be of any age, sex or breed, but young Standardbreds have been over-represented, and a familial predisposition has been reported in some cases (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000).

Lymphoplasmacytic enterocolitis (LPE)

LPE is characterised by infiltration of lymphocytes and plasma cells at the level of the lamina propria of the GIT (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). Although only 20 cases were reported at the end of the 20th century (Schumacher et al., 2000), according to the histopathological results of intestinal biopsies, the incidence of this disease has increased more recently (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014). LPE can occur at any age, and the disease has no breed or sex predilection (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). In small animals, the histopathological features of this type of IBD and intestinal lymphoma are similar, and it has been speculated that LPE may precede the development of intestinal lymphoma (Couto et al., 2018; Sogame et al., 2018), which might also be the case in horses (Lindberg et al., 1996; Schumacher et al., 2000).

Eosinophilic enterocolitis

Eosinophilic enterocolitis (EE) is characterised by an inflammatory cell infiltration at the level of the intestinal mucosa, dominated by eosinophils (Kalck, 2009). Multisystemic eosinophilic epitheliotropic disease (MEED) has been referred to, using many different terms, such as eosinophilic gastroenteritis, eosinophilic enterocolitis, eosinophilic granulomatosis, hypereosinophilia syndrome and exfoliative dermatitis and stomatitis (Schumacher et al., 2000). However, as it is characterised by eosinophilic infiltration of the intestine and other organs, the term MEED should be preferred (Kalck, 2009). Horses of any age, sex and breed may be affected, but the disease has been described more commonly in young (2-4 years of age) Standardbreds and Thoroughbreds (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). When there is only diffuse eosinophilic infiltration of the small or large intestine without involvement of other organs, the term diffuse eosinophilic enterocolitis is appropriate (DEE) (Edwards et al., 2000; Mäkinen et al., 2008). Since the end of the 20th century, a novel, more focal eosinophilic infiltrative disease has been reported with increasing prevalence (Edwards et al., 2000; Proudman and Kipar, 2006). It is characterised by localised circumscribed eosinophilic infiltrative lesions both in

small (Archer et al., 2014; Mäkinen et al., 2008) and large intestine (Edwards et al., 2000). Transmural infiltration of the small intestine dominated by eosinophils has been referred to as idiopathic eosinophilic enteritis, multifocal eosinophilic enteritis, circumferential mural bands or, more consistently, idiopathic focal eosinophilic enteritis (IFEE) (Proudman and Kipar, 2006; Mäkinen et al., 2008; Archer et al., 2014). Less frequently, idiopathic focal infiltration of eosinophils confined to the large colon has also been reported (Edwards et al., 2000); thus, this can be referred to as idiopathic focal eosinophilic colitis (IFEC). No clear cause has been identified to explain these inflammatory infiltrates (Edwards et al., 2000; Mäkinen et al., 2008; Archer et al., 2014), although intestinal nematodes were strongly suspected to be involved (Schumacher et al., 2000). In addition to inducing local immediate hypersensitivity reaction, that results in eosinophilic infiltrates, parasites also contain endogenous factors that directly attract eosinophils (Cohen et al., 1992).

Clinical and diagnostic evaluation of horses with IBD

Although many clinicians advocate for clearer guidelines for the diagnosis of IBD (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Olofsson et al., 2015), in the author's opinion the clinical investigations should proceed stepwise, starting with minimally invasive procedures, and progressing to more invasive diagnostic methods (Table 1). Since IBDs are characterised by unspecific clinical signs and highly variable results from all the listed diagnostic tests, the diagnosis is usually reached by the exclusion of other possible and more common causes of those signs (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Fintl et al., 2020; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Kalck, 2009; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018; Olofsson et al., 2015).

In Table 1, a flowchart is provided for the diagnostic work-up of a horse suspected of suffering from IBD from the less to the most invasive.

History and clinical signs

As already mentioned, clinical signs of IBD are nonspecific; thus, firstly, it is necessary to exclude possible other more common causes (Archer et al., 2014).

Since the most reported clinical sign of IBD is weight loss despite a good appetite, the investigation should start with the evaluation of the animal's diet, teeth and parasite load (Kalck, 2009; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Body condition scoring (BCS) is an important component of the initial physical examination for a horse presenting with IBD, and it has been found to be positively correlated with the duration of clinical signs; thus, it was speculated that more severely affected animals, losing condition quickly, were probably referred for evaluation sooner (Metcalfe et al., 2013).

A history of mild, recurrent colic is also common in horses with IBD (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Trachsel et al., 2010), but acute severe colic episodes necessitating surgery can also occur (Edwards et al., 2000; Mäkinen et al., 2008; Archer et al., 2014). The mild colic may be due to changes in motility caused by the infiltrates within the intestinal walls and, possibly, by the reduction in interstitial cells of Cajal (Fintl et al., 2020; Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). These cells are considered the pacemaker of the intestinal smooth muscle cells, and they have been found

TABLE 1: Flow chart for the diagnostic investigation of suspected IBD

		Horses presented with: Weight loss despite good appetite Chronic diarrhoea Recurrent colic	
First step	Check the diet. Exclude: Dental problems Intestinal parasites (Kalck, 2009; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Schumacher et al., 2000).	<u>Complete physical examination</u> (including rectal examination): Skin lesions [□] Ventral/limb oedemas [□] (Kalck, 2009; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Schumacher et al., 2000).	<u>Blood work:</u> Exclude infection, hepatic and renal diseases. Anaemia [□] , especially in GE due to chronic disease and malabsorption of elements involved in erythropoiesis (Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000). Frequently hypoproteinaemia and hypoalbuminaemia [□] (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018) Elevated hepatic enzymes [□] in MEED, if there's liver involvement (Bosseler et al., 2013; Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000).
Second step	<u>Transabdominal ultrasonography:</u> Sometimes increased thickness of small intestine [□] (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kalck, 2009). Occasionally lymphadenopathy [□] (Kalck, 2009).	<u>Abdominocentesis:</u> Usually normal transudate in IBD (Kalck, 2009; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). It may be altered in case of peritonitis, intra-abdominal neoplasia or abscess (Edwards et al., 2000; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).	
Third step	<u>Absorption tests:</u> Decreased in case of diffuse infiltrative disease of small intestine [□] (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Kalck, 2009; Metcalfe et al., 2013).	<u>Histopathology of noninvasive biopsy samples</u> (duodenal or rectal): Infiltration with inflammatory cells [□] (Lindberg et al., 1996; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Boshuizen et al., 2018). Not useful in segmental diseases (Kalck, 2009). Limitation: lack of standardisation for the interpretation (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).	
Fourth step	<u>Laparoscopy/Laparotomy:</u> For collection of full-thickness intestinal samples (Kalck, 2009) May also help to exclude/confirm presence of intra-abdominal masses (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1996; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).		

GE, Granulomatous enteritis; MEED, Multisystemic eosinophilic epitheliotropic disease; [□] = red flags of possible IBD

to be significantly reduced in the myenteric plexus region of IBD horses (Fintl et al., 2020). The more severe colic episodes are hypothesised to be due to abnormal fermentation of excessive amounts of carbohydrates within the large colon. These carbohydrates normally would have been absorbed within the small intestine, but, because of the cellular infiltrates, they remain in the intestine and reach the colon where they undergo fermentation by colonic flora, resulting in excessive gas production (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). Excessive gas may result in spasmodic colic or progress to a displacement or torsion of the large colon (Kalck, 2009). In the case of focal lesions, these may result in obstruction of ingesta proximally; thus, moderate-severe colic pain might develop (Archer et al., 2014). Furthermore, the longer these lesions persisted without treatment, the more advanced serosal changes have been described, ultimately leading to peritonitis (Edwards et al., 2000).

Horses with IBD may also show diarrhoea and, due to the chronic nature of the disease, if diarrhoea is present, it is usually a chronic or intermittent sign (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Mair, 2002; Valle et al., 2013). Faecal consistency is reported to vary from watery to semisolid and, in some cases, there are episodes of chronic diarrhoea interspersed with periods of normal faeces (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). The large colon of horses has an enormous capacity of water reabsorption; thus, it is possible

that certain degrees of intestinal inflammation are present also with normal faecal output (Kalck, 2009).

Physical examination

In most cases, physical examination appears normal (Boshuizen et al., 2018). Heart rate may be elevated in association with the degree of pain, and only slight dehydration may be present (Edwards et al., 2000). Increased rectal temperature is an uncommon finding in horses with IBD (Kalck, 2009).

The presence of ventral or limb oedema can be related to the hypoproteinaemia that it is usually present with these diseases; thus, it should be carefully evaluated and eventually investigated with blood analysis (Kalck, 2009; Metcalfe et al., 2013).

Since some of the IBDs, such as MEED and GE, may also be associated with skin lesions, a thorough evaluation of the skin and coat of presenting cases is indicated, keeping in mind that hair loss on the caudal aspect of hindlimbs could be due to skin irritation associated with chronic intermittent diarrhoea (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000).

Blood work

Serum chemistry and haematology may help exclude involvement of infections and chronic disorders that can be responsible for poor body condition, such as hepatic, renal or

cardiac diseases (Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Horses with IBD may have a completely normal blood work, but more frequently they present with hypoproteinaemia due to hypoalbuminaemia that may be accompanied by reduced, normal or elevated globulin concentrations (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Usually, in horses the hypoproteinaemia is more commonly associated with increased loss than with decreased production that may only occur with severe chronic liver diseases (Bergero and Nery, 2008). Aside from the GIT, proteins can be lost through the urinary tract or be accumulated in the third space; thus, urinalysis and thoracic or abdominal ultrasound to exclude the presence of effusions should be part of the initial evaluation (Hines, 2018). In horses with IBD, the major cause of hypoproteinaemia has been shown to result from excessive loss of proteins into the intestinal tract (Lindberg et al., 1985). The mechanisms that may contribute to this loss include: ulceration of the gastrointestinal mucosa with exudation of plasma, lymphatic obstruction, passive diffusion through intracellular spaces, intracellular loss, increased permeability of capillaries and venules and altered cellular metabolism (Hodgson and Allen, 1982; Mair, 2002).

Anaemia is frequently reported in patients with GE, but it may be present also in the other forms of IBD, and it is suspected to be associated with chronic disease and malabsorption of elements involved in erythropoiesis (Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000). The white blood cells count of horses with IBD is usually within the reference range, but both neutropenia and neutrophilia have been reported (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000).

Liver enzymes have been reported to be elevated in some horses with IBD, in particular in MEED cases in which eosinophilic infiltrates may also be present in the hepatic parenchyma (Bosseler et al., 2013; Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000).

Transabdominal ultrasound

An association has been reported between the presence of thickened small intestinal loops on transabdominal ultrasound and during rectal palpation (Boshuizen et al., 2018). Since rectal examination allows the examination only of the most caudal portion of the abdomen, abdominal ultrasonography permits a more complete noninvasive view of the GIT (Ceriotti et al., 2016; Kalck, 2009). Furthermore, in cases with rectal biopsy results compatible with IBD, the increased thickness of small intestine can be confirmed ultrasonographically (Ceriotti et al., 2016). Normal small intestinal wall thickness is around 2–4 mm (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Occasionally, lymphadenopathy can be also visualised with transabdominal ultrasound (Kalck, 2009). Furthermore, transabdominal ultrasonography could also allow detection of peritoneal effusion and abdominal masses; and it may be useful in the assessment of other abdominal organs such as the liver, the spleen and kidneys (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).

Abdominocentesis

Abdominocentesis should be performed in any horses with colic and/or hypoproteinaemia to rule out presence of strangulating lesions, peritonitis, abdominal abscesses and abdominal neoplasia (Edwards et al., 2000; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). In most cases, the peritoneal fluid cytology of horses with IBD is a normal

transudate (Kalck, 2009; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018), although increased amounts of eosinophils can be found in some eosinophilic enterocolitis cases (Southwood et al., 2000).

Absorption tests

In the diagnostic work-up of IBD, both glucose and D-xylose absorption tests have been used since they evaluate the absorption of substances through the GIT (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Metcalfe et al., 2013). The glucose absorption test (GAT) is relatively simple and does not require specialised equipment (Durham et al., 2019). In a healthy horse, the plasma glucose level should rise to higher than 85% over the baseline between 60 and 120 minutes after the oral administration of glucose (Murphy et al., 1997). If the peak is between 15% and 85%, we refer to partial malabsorption. However, this is not specific for a small intestinal problem as it can also be due to enhanced use of glucose or delayed gastric emptying. Total malabsorption occurs when the peak is below 15%; in this case diffuse, small intestinal disease is highly suspected (Kalck, 2009). Although the test is quite straightforward, several factors can influence the results, including diet, gastric emptying rate, intestinal transit, age, hormonal effects and the metabolic state of the horse (Murphy et al., 1997; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).

The D-xylose absorption test is a more specialised diagnostic test that is not dependent on hormonal or metabolic factors; nevertheless, it can still be affected by the rate of gastric emptying, intestinal motility, bacterial overgrowth and renal clearance (Kalck, 2009; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).

Remarkably, a normal absorption test does not exclude IBD or other infiltrative enteral diseases (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kalck, 2009). The reported results of these kinds of tests in horses with IBDs have been variable as, if the inflammatory process is localised in the large intestine, it does not compromise sugar absorption, but it will more likely cause diarrhoea (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Lindberg et al., 1985). Historically, it was reported that horses with GE presented malabsorption, while horses with eosinophilic enterocolitis had a delayed but normal peak of absorption (Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000). In a recent retrospective study (Boshuizen et al., 2018), an abnormal aspect of the duodenum seen during gastroduodenoscopy was found to be associated with an abnormal GAT. In another recent study (Kaikkonen et al., 2014), inadequate D-xylose absorption was a significant clinicopathological predictor of survival identified, thus supporting the use of this test in the diagnostic evaluation of horses suspected of having IBD. It is the author's opinion that an abnormal test result should be expected with more diffuse, chronic and severe diseases, regardless the type of IBD.

Histopathology of biopsy samples

Exploratory laparotomy to obtain full-thickness intestinal biopsies is one method of achieving a precise diagnosis (Lindberg et al., 1996; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). With this approach, the presence of intra-abdominal abscesses and neoplasia can also be detected. Nevertheless, it is invasive and affected horses are not always good candidates for major exploratory surgeries because of an increased chance for occurrence of complications caused by hypoproteinaemia and the catabolic state of the patient (Kalck, 2009). Exploratory laparoscopy is minimally invasive, but up to now it has not routinely been used because

obtaining full-thickness biopsies is quite challenging with this technique (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Other less invasive methods to obtain biopsy samples from the GIT are duodenal biopsies via gastroscopy or rectal biopsies (Lindberg et al., 1996).

Gastroscopy can confirm or rule out involvement of gastric ulceration, and it is also suitable for diagnosis of gastric carcinoma (Tamzali, 2006). A duodenal biopsy can be diagnostic of IBD if the duodenum is involved (Boshuizen et al., 2018); however, in segmental diseases, such as IFEE, the lesion may be missed (Kalck, 2009). A disadvantage of this technique is the small sample size that can be obtained from the biopsy channel of a gastroscope (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1996). Furthermore, in some cases of IBD, no additional details have been obtained by duodenal biopsies, while rectal biopsies have been slightly more informative (Metcalfe et al., 2013).

Rectal biopsy, on the other hand, is easily performed at low cost (Lindberg et al., 1996). Samples are usually taken approximately one arm's length from the dorsolateral portion of the rectum (Kalck, 2009; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Histopathological findings at this level may not represent the entire GIT, though it is valid for duodenal biopsies (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018; Stewart et al., 2018). Furthermore, another limitation is the lack of information to which extent variations can be considered as normal in a rectal biopsy (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018; Olofsson et al., 2015). Extensive work has been done by the World Small Animals Veterinary Association Gastrointestinal Standardisation Group to classify the degree and type of inflammation of the different GIT segments, and they also provided templates to assist clinicians and pathologists in the histopathological interpretation in order to assign a score at the changes encountered (Day et al., 2008). In horses, unfortunately, this standardisation is lacking and experienced pathologists cannot therefore rely on a scoring system to assess equine intestinal biopsies. We can only find a list of normal and abnormal findings according to the type of cells and location (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Neutrophils are normally present within the lamina propria but are not found in the surface epithelium or crypts; thus when observed in these locations, they are always considered as pathological (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1996; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). Lymphocytes and plasma cells also can normally be found in the lamina propria of the rectum, but hypercellularity is considered abnormal (Lindberg et al., 1996). Nevertheless, the increase in lymphocytes and plasma cells does not justify a diagnosis of LPE, as this may be found with a variety of intestinal conditions such as cyathostomiasis, granulomatous disease, alimentary lymphoma and LPE; thus, it probably represents a nonspecific pattern of hyper-reactivity in the gut mucosa rather than a pathological defined entity (Kalck, 2009; Lindberg et al., 1996; Mair et al., 2006). Eosinophilic infiltration of the lamina propria and submucosal layers of the rectum also can be normal (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Lindberg et al., 1996). Furthermore, notably important, in more than half of the horses with a diagnosis of IBD no histopathological changes were detected in the rectal biopsy (Kaikkonen et al., 2014).

Treatment

The aim of the treatment is to decrease the horse's exposure to possible dietary, parasitic or environmental antigens (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000).

In dogs, the treatment has also been standardised and its first step consists of a dietary modification towards a novel source of protein and carbohydrates or towards a commercially available hydrolysed protein diet (Jergens and Simpson, 2012; Kalenyak et al., 2018; Kalenyak et al., 2019). The diet should then be strictly followed for at least 14 days before a further therapy is added (Kalenyak et al., 2019). In horses, instead, no clear indications are available and usually the dietary recommendations are only part of the initial treatment. Highly digestible high fibre feed should be administered in small and frequent amounts to improve digestion and absorption (Kalck, 2009). Corn oil can be added to the ration to achieve adequate levels of energy avoiding the use of carbohydrates (Kalck, 2009; van der Kolk et al., 2012). The possible link between feeding management and development of IBD has been suggested in several equine studies; however, no study has been able to pinpoint this (Boshuizen et al., 2018; van der Kolk et al., 2012). The discovery of gluten-sensitive enteropathy in a horse suffering from IBD highlights the importance of the diet in the treatment and control of these types of GIT diseases (van der Kolk et al., 2012).

Even low levels of parasites that normally accumulate between deworming treatments can be a trigger for inflammation. Therefore, more frequent administrations of anthelmintic therapies are advocated for horses with IBD (Kalck, 2009; Schumacher et al., 2000). However, again, there is no consensus on which drugs should be used, how frequently and for how long. Furthermore, one important aspect when using anthelmintics is the concern of development of widespread resistance (Oliver-Espinosa, 2018).

Corticosteroids are the treatment of choice in horses diagnosed with IBD (Schumacher et al., 2000). Usually, a prolonged, tapering course is required, and administration is initially parenteral because of the malabsorption process (Kalck, 2009). Similar to all the other aspects of diagnosis and treatment of IBD in horses, there are no particular indications on doses and duration of the therapy. The treatment is tapered and adjusted according to the response and the development of adverse effects. Systemic administration of corticosteroids to horses has been associated with several adverse effects, including adrenocortical suppression and dysfunction, laminitis, hepatopathy, muscle wasting, altered bone metabolism and increased susceptibility to infections (Dauvillier et al., 2011).

Additional treatments that have been suggested for horses with IBD and are summarised in **Table 2**.

In conclusion, extrapolation of data from man or other species to horses is difficult due to the differences on GIT anatomy and physiology (Mullen et al., 2018). Nevertheless, while there are no peer-reviewed studies, many practitioners developed their own treatment protocols with anecdotal reports of success (Feary and Hassel, 2006). More systematic studies are needed to dictate clear guidelines for the equine species.

Prognosis

Although at the end of the 20th century the response to medical treatment was reported to be extremely poor (Hodgson and Allen 1982; Lindberg et al., 1985; Schumacher et al., 2000), more recently the prognosis has been fair to

TABLE 2: Alternative medical treatment proposed for IBD cases

Treatment	Hypothesised/documentated effect	Reference
Metronidazole	Antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory	Kalck, 2009
Hydroxyurea	Antineoplastic drug used in humans suffering from hypereosinophilia syndrome; suggested for the treatment of MEED in horses	Bosseler et al., 2013
Sulfasalazine	Colon-specific prodrug used for the treatment of Crohn's disease in humans; reported to be successful in one horse with chronic diarrhoea without a definitive diagnosis	Valle et al., 2013
Cyclosporine, Azathioprine, Chlorambucil, Mycophenolate	Immune suppressive drugs used in dogs with IBD; not studied in horses	Craven and Washabau, 2019
Probiotics	Applied for a variety of GIT disorders in humans and small animals; inconsistent results in horses	Jergens and Simpson, 2012; Schoster et al., 2014; Grzeškowiak et al., 2015; Schoster et al., 2016; Schoster, 2018; Kim et al., 2019
Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) supplementations	Used in humans and dogs with IBD to decrease the production of arachidonic acid-derived pro-inflammatory eicosanoids in favour of anti-inflammatory eicosanoids; not studied in horses	Calder, 2013; Kalenyak et al., 2019
Faecal microbiota transplant (FMT)	Approved for the use only in humans with <i>Clostridium difficile</i> infection; recently gained interest in small animals, ruminants and horses	Cammarota et al., 2014; DePeters and George, 2014; Julliard and Grimm, 2016; Costa and Weese, 2018; Mullen et al., 2018; Pereira et al., 2018; Murcia, 2019

GIT, Gastrointestinal tract; IBD, Inflammatory bowel disease; MEED, Multisystemic eosinophilic epitheliotropic disease

moderate with 65% of the horses with IBD surviving at least 3 years (Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Kalck, 2009). It is possible that this difference is due to a prompter diagnosis that allows to treat cases when the disease is still mild, this may explain why the prognosis has improved. If the disease is focal, surgical resection of the affected bowel can be curative (Edwards et al., 2000; Mäkinen et al., 2008; Archer et al., 2014) but a complete recovery has been described also following manual decompression of the affected segment without resection (Perez Olmos et al., 2006; Proudman and Kipar, 2006).

Regarding markers associated with survival, Metcalfe et al., (2013) reported an association between hypoproteinaemia and nonsurvival in horses referred for investigation of weight loss despite good appetite. Nevertheless, Kaikkonen et al., (2014) in their study population did not find that hypoalbuminaemia was a risk factor for nonsurvival, instead they suggested that a low peak xylose concentration in absorption testing could be associated with a less favourable prognosis.

Furthermore, considering the small sample size of the cases described in the literature and the variable results of the diagnostic test, it is possible that some associations with survival or nonsurvival are confounding factors rather than true associations. In fact, cases with severe abnormalities, that is complete malabsorption or alterations on histopathological examination of intestinal biopsies, at least in the past were more likely to be given a hopeless prognosis, increasing the likelihood of the owner opting for euthanasia (Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Metcalfe et al., 2013).

Although the overall prognosis for long-term survival in horses with IBD has improved in the last few years, there are no specific prognostic markers and each patient should be fully evaluated with blood work, abdominal ultrasound,

absorption tests and histopathological examination of biopsy samples (Boshuizen et al., 2018; Kaikkonen et al., 2014; Metcalfe et al., 2013; Oliver-Espinosa, 2018). The initial response to treatment can be interpreted as an indicator of a better or poorer prognosis (Kaikkonen et al., 2014).

Conclusions

IBD is a general term that collect a multitude of different diseases with different aetiology and pathophysiology. There is an impellent need for consensus on the nomenclature, diagnostic work-up, diet, treatment and management of horses suspected of IBD.

The present review provides initial guidelines to assist practitioners dealing with suspected cases.

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